

MICROMECHANICAL INVESTIGATION OF RESIDUAL STRESSES AND STRENGTH OF CROSS-PLY LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

Micromechanical analysis of composites with Finite Elements Method (FEM) has been very popular recently. The overall behaviour of a composite can be predicted by modelling in its constituents' level. It is assumed that the fibres lie inside the matrix in square or hexagonally packed arrays. These are called representative volume elements (RVE). This method has been applied to unidirectional (UD) composites for detailed micromechanical analysis in a wide range of studies [1-12]. However there is few studies dealing with cross-ply (XP) laminates. Xia et. al [13] developed a 3D multi-cell meso/micro-mechanical FE model for the overall mechanical behaviour of $[0,90_3,0]_T$ glass fibre/epoxy laminate with 52.5% fibre volume fraction (V_f). Progressive failure analysis was performed by implementing Maximum Strain Failure criterion to the viscous epoxy matrix under tensile loading. It was found that model prediction is in good agreement with experimental observation in terms of global stress-strain response and damage initiation and its propagation. Chen et. al. [14] investigated the effect of viscoelasticity of matrix on the evolution of process-induced residual stresses of the same composite for UD and XP laminates by using 3D square packed RVEs. It was found that, viscous behaviour of matrix plays an important role in the evaluation of residual stress and higher cooling rate results in higher residual stress than lower cooling rate. Also it was presented that different ply orientations generate different residual stresses in magnitude and distribution. Higher residual stresses are induced in XP laminates than UD. Xia et. al [15] developed unified (for both thermal and mechanical loading) boundary conditions (BCs) for various types of micromechanical RVE models. It was observed that the proposed BCs satisfy the boundary displacement periodicity and also stress periodicity of the RVE model under general multi-axial loading

conditions. These BCs are suitable for RVE models of any angle-ply (AP) and XP laminates. Zhang et. al. [16] developed the work done in Ref. [14] in their study. They presented a meso/micro-mechanical study of glass fibre reinforced viscoelastic epoxy resin XP laminates during and after high temperature curing process. Generation of cooling-induced residual stresses/strains and their influence under subsequent mechanical loading were investigated. It was seen that higher cooling rate results in higher residual stresses. Shrinkage at the end of the cure cycle and local residual strains have significant effect on the response of laminate under subsequently applied mechanical loading. For example, the location of damage initiation and its propagation paths are different for cases with and without residual strains. Abolfathi et. al. [17] developed a FE micromechanical model to efficiently determine the elastic properties of bidirectional fibrous composites. RVE model for UD, XP and AP laminates were subjected to 6 independent load cases. 4 different composite materials were tested. A good agreement between the micromechanical model and the stiffness-compliance solutions from Classical Lamination Theory (CLT) was obtained. Naik et. al [18] developed the work of Abolfathi et. al. [17] for glass fibre reinforced viscoelastic epoxy resin. Similar to Ref. [17], viscoelastic properties of the composite were determined under 6 different load cases. Hexagonal and square packed RVEs for UD and square packed RVE for XP laminate were tested and compared for different V_f . It was found that square packed RVE is stiffer than hexagonal for UD composite and higher stresses are induced in XP laminate than UD when loaded in normal directions. Karami et. al. [19] developed the work of Abolfathi et. al. [17] for prediction of residual stress formation and the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) due to a unit temperature increase for glass fibre and

carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites. Effects of fibre cross angle and V_f were investigated. It was found that as the fibre cross angle increases, residual stresses induced in fibre and resin of carbon fibre/epoxy composite increase, however as the V_f increases, residual stresses induced in fibres decrease while the residual stresses induced in resin of glass fibre/epoxy increase and CTE decreases.

This study is a further improvement of authors' previous work [12] in which FE micromechanical model was developed to predict the elastic moduli of UD AS4/8552, to investigate its behaviour throughout Manufacturer's Recommended Cure Cycle (MRCC) and to assess the damage progression under resin dominated loading modes, by taking into account the effect of process-induced residual stress. In this study, the same procedure is applied for XP laminate. First of all, in order to validate the model, (RVE and geometry) the material in Ref. [17] is considered for elastic moduli prediction. Predictions show good agreement with Ref. [17]. Then AS4/8552 is considered and its elastic moduli are predicted. Secondly, MRCC is modelled by implementing the instantaneous strain and temperature dependent properties of resin through its cure cycle into the model by using ABAQUS user defined subroutine UMAT. Finally, progressive damage assessment is modelled with another user defined subroutine, USDFLD under tensile loadings with and without the effect of process-induced residual stress. Elastic moduli and strain variation throughout MRCC is presented, especially at some specific points. Global stress-strain responses are presented and strength values are compared with UD ply and also with experimental data available in literature. Damage progressions are presented for normal load modes.

2 Finite Element Analysis

2.1 Representative Volume Element

ABAQUS® [20] is used for FE analysis. 3D square packed RVE is selected in this study. 8 noded brick elements (C3D8) are used to mesh the model. Results converge when the element size is less than or equal to 0.2 μm . RVEs with 0.2 μm element size are shown in Figure 1 where the fibres and resin are represented with different colours. Regardless of the

volume fraction, dimensions of the RVE should follow the parameters of the square geometry. A whole RVE is used for shear loadings (to predict shear moduli) as in Ref. [17] and quarter RVE is used for normal loadings. In whole RVE, the origin of the model is the mid-point of the model and in quarter RVE, origin is the point behind the point "E" in Figure 1.

In FE micromechanical analysis, BCs are very important for periodicity and symmetry of RVE. BCs for normal and thermal loading are given in Table 1. Nodes on $x=0$, $y=0$ and $z=0$ planes are restricted (R) to move in their normal direction but they are free (F) to move in perpendicular directions. Also, in order to keep the edges planar during the deformation, nodes on opposite surfaces are constrained (C) to move the same amount in normal directions. BCs for shear loading are different. BCs for shear load modes are given in Table 2. For example, for τ_{23} , node at the origin of the whole RVE is restricted to move in any direction, all nodes on bottom ($z=-L$) and top ($z=L$) planes are constrained to move equally in y axis but in opposite directions and similarly all nodes on left ($y=-2L$) and right ($y=2L$) planes are constrained to move equally in z axis but in opposite directions. Required modifications are applied for τ_{12} and τ_{13} load modes as presented in Table 2.

2.2 Prediction of Elastic Moduli

The material modelled in this study is AS4/8552 with $V_f=57.4\%$. Constituents' properties can be found in [10, 21]. For normal loading, unit strain is applied in the direction of concern and the modulus in that direction is the global stress induced in that direction which is the average of local stresses in the RVE. For shear load modes, unit shear strain is applied to the corner nodes of the RVE in direction of concern; resulting global stress is the regarding shear modulus. For example for τ_{23} , unit strain is applied in $+y$ & $+z$ and $-y$ & $-z$ directions to the corner nodes "A" and "D" in Figure 1 respectively.

2.3 Prediction of Thermochemical strains and Residual Stresses

Residual stress developing in a XP AS4/8552 throughout the MRCC, described in Ref. [21], is investigated. In addition to this, shrinkage of resin during MRCC and elastic moduli development

through cure are investigated in details. Previously, Ersoy et. al. [10] predicted the development of thermochemical strains and elastic modulus of the 8552 resin as the cure progresses by using Group Interaction Modelling (GIM) as seen in Figures 2 and 3 respectively. Gelation of the composite takes place in the 130th min. of the cure cycle. Vitrification takes place in the 45th minutes after 180 °C dwell begins [10]. Development of thermochemical strains and the modulus of the resin are modelled by implementing these instantaneous strain and temperature dependent properties of resin during MRCC into the user-defined subroutine UMAT. Residual stress induced in composite is calculated by using equation 1 for resin in UMAT. Residual stress and CTE predictions for XP laminate are compared with the values of UD ply [12] and some experimental data available in literature.

$$\{DSTRESS(i, j)\} = [C] \cdot \{DSTRAN(i, j) - \delta_{ij} \cdot d\epsilon_{th}\} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- [C] : Stiffness matrix
DSTRESS(i,j) : Incremental stress array
DSTRAN(i,j) : Incremental mechanical strain array
 $\delta_{ij} \cdot d\epsilon_{ij}$: Incremental strain due to chemical and/or thermal effects

2.4 Progressive Failure Analysis

In this study, only tensile loadings are taken into account. Progressive failure analysis of a XP AS4/8552 laminate is modelled with stiffness reduction method in conjunction with ABAQUS user defined subroutines USDFLD and UMAT as in [12]. Failure behaviour of AS4/8552 is investigated by implementing Maximum Principal, Raghava's and Bauwen's modified von-Misses (MVM) Failure criteria to 8552 resin and AS4 fibre in USDFLD with and without residual stress. Details of Raghava's and Bauwen's MVM Failure criteria can be seen in Equations 2 and 3 respectively as defined in [5-6].

$$\frac{\sigma_{VM}^2}{\sigma_r^c \sigma_r^t} + \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_r^t} - \frac{1}{\sigma_r^c} \right) I_1 = 1 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_r^t} - \frac{1}{\sigma_r^c} \right) I_1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_r^t} + \frac{1}{\sigma_r^c} \right) \sigma_{VM} = 1 \quad (3)$$

Where:

- σ_r^c : Compressive strength of resin
 σ_r^t : Tensile strength of resin
 σ_{VM} : von-Misses stress induced in resin
 I_1 : First invariant induced in resin

Strength values of resin are required for each Failure Criteria as seen in Equations 2 and 3. Tensile strength of 8552 resin is available in [21], but the compression strength is not. Compression strength of 3501-6 epoxy resin is known as 250 MPa, and same compressive/tensile strength ratio is assumed to be valid for 8552 epoxy resin which gives a compressive strength of 300 MPa for 8552 resin. The interfacial adhesive strength properties are assumed to be equal to cohesive strength of the resin. Predicted strength values of XP laminate and damage path after its initiation are presented. Damage assessment of XP laminate is compared with UD ply.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Elastic Moduli Prediction

First of all, elastic moduli of "Composite #2" in Ref. [17] are predicted to verify the model for XP laminates. Prediction of this model is compared with Ref. [17] in Table 3. As it is seen, results are almost same with [17]. Then, same procedure is applied for AS4/8552. Deformations under each load case are given in Figure 4. Predictions for elastic moduli of XP AS4/8552 are given and compared with UD and some experimental results in Table 4. Very limited experimental data are available for XP laminate. In [22] E_1 and ν_{13} are obtained with respect to ASTM D-3039 and ASTM D-6641 test standards respectively. In addition to these, CTE predictions for XP laminate are compared with measurements and as presented in Table 4. Experiments were performed in Thermo-Mechanical Analyser (TMA) previously by Ersoy. In the experiments 6x6x4 mm and 6x6x1 mm specimens were used for UD and XP composites respectively. Specimens were equilibrated at 30°C and heated from 30 to 250°C at a rate of 2 K/min in a helium atmosphere. An expansion probe with a flat face of diameter 3.66 mm was used, and 10 mN force was applied. A fresh specimen was used for each experiment so that all specimens had the same thermal history. Three

specimens were run for each orientation of each sample. Predictions obtained in this study are in very good agreement with measurements.

Stress distributions for each load mode under applied unit strains in various directions can be seen in Figures 5-9. Two different views are presented for the σ_{22} to view the location of maximum stress induced in the region where the fibres are closest to each other in the RVE. If Table 4 and Figures 5-9 are examined together, it can be seen that the elastic moduli in each direction are the average value of regarding stress distributions.

3.2 Cure Shrinkage and Residual Stress Analysis

Strain variation in transverse direction during MRCC simulation of XP and UD AS4/8552 is plotted in Figure 10. As it is seen, strain variation of XP laminate is almost the twice of the UD ply in transverse direction. In order to see the strain variation in details, some values at some specific points throughout the MRCC is emphasized such as at the gelation point (GP), at the vitrification point (VP), at the beginning of cooling stage (CP) and at the end of the MRCC. They are presented in Table 5. CTEs in each direction are calculated by using incremental modulus and strain of resin during cooling from 180 °C to 20 °C and they are presented in Table 6. As one can see that, prediction of CTEs by using glassy values of constituents as in Table 4 is very similar to the prediction by using incremental strain and elastic moduli as in Table 6. In addition to this, CTE predictions in this study are compared with measurements as stated in Section 3.1. Details of the experiments are given in Section 3.1 and the measurements with UD plies are given in Table 7. Predictions obtained by using incremental strain and elastic moduli of resin are in very good agreement with measurements. Thus, knowing the CTE of any composite enables to see the cooling stage and also predict the residual stress development of any composite during cooling from cure temperature to room temperature by using the micromechanical model developed in this study.

As stated in [12], most of the residual stresses develop at the cooling stage of the composite. Figure 11-12 present the residual Maximum Principal Stress distribution at the beginning and end of the cooling respectively. As seen, the magnitude of the residual Maximum Principal Stress increases from

17.17 MPa to 101 MPa. Three failure criteria are considered for the failure analysis as stated above. Failure parameter distributions due to residual stress at the end of the cure cycle in terms of the other two criteria are presented in Figures 13-14. Comparison of the maximum value of each failure parameter with UD ply is presented in Table 8 where the magnitude of Maximum Principal Stress is given in terms of its ratio to tensile strength of resin. As Chen found in [14] for glass fibre reinforced epoxy, higher residual stresses are formed in XP AS4/8552 than UD. One important result is that, composite seems to fail at the end of the cure cycle with respect to Raghava's MVM Failure criteria, since the failure parameter exceeds unity. Therefore this criterion is not considered for progressive failure analysis because resin is already failed at the end of the MRCC.

3.3 Progressive Failure Analysis

First of all, tensile strength and damage path under transverse tensile loading (in y (2) direction) are presented. Stress-strain curves with respect to Maximum Principal and Bauwen's MVM failure criteria are presented in Figure 15. Transverse tensile strength of cross-ply AS4/8552 is 48 MPa with respect to Maximum Principal failure criterion and it is 44 MPa with respect to Bauwen's Modified von-Misses failure criterion. Without the effect of residual stress, they increase to 86 and 90 MPa respectively. Comparison between transverse tensile strength predictions of XP AS4/8552 with UD are given in Tables 9 and 10. Since hexagonally packed RVE is used in [12], transverse tensile strength of UD is direction dependent. One can see the detrimental effect of XP sequence on transverse tensile strength of AS4/8552 in Table 9 with the effect of residual stress. However, this is not valid for the case without residual stress. Transverse tensile strength predictions for XP are between the σ_y^T and σ_z^T of UD ply. It can be said that progressive failure analysis is more realistic when the process-induced residual stress is considered. Damage evolutions with the effect of residual stress are similar for each failure criteria. Therefore only the damage path in resin under Maximum Principal Stress criterion is sketched in Figure 16.

Failure modes in longitudinal directions (x(1) and/or z(3) directions) are fibre dominant. First, matrix

cracking is expected to occur, and then the final failure occurs at the increment when the fibre fails. This situation is observed within this study. Stress-strain curves under longitudinal tensile loading of XP AS4/8552 laminate are plotted in Figures 17 and 18. Figure 17 is the stress-strain response when the Maximum Principal Failure criterion is applied to both resin and fibre while Figure 18 is the response when Bauwen's MVM is applied to resin and Maximum Principal Stress Failure criterion is applied to the fibre. In Figure 17, it is seen that first matrix cracking occurs when σ_1 or $\sigma_3=198$ MPa with the effect of process-induced residual stress but when this effect is neglected, matrix cracking occurs at $\sigma_1=610$ MPa as indicated. One can see that, residual stress has beneficial effect on the longitudinal tensile stress-strain response of XP AS4/8552. Because without the effect of residual stress, final failure occurs at $\sigma_1=1137$ MPa and it increases to $\sigma_1=1172$ MPa when the process-induced residual stress is considered with respect to Maximum Principal Failure criterion. In Figure 18, it is seen that, by considering the process-induced residual stresses, first matrix cracking of XP AS4/8552 occurs at $\sigma_1=95$ MPa with respect to Bauwen's MVM Failure criteria and without this effect, crack initiates at $\sigma_1=648$ MPa in the resin as indicated. Beneficial effect of process-induced residual stress is seen again. Because without residual stress, final failure occurs at $\sigma_1=1153$ MPa and it increases to 1174 MPa with residual stress with respect to Bauwen's MVM Failure criterion. This is due to the compressive residual stresses induced on fibres by resin shrinkage and contraction. In literature, only final failure values are available as experimental strength. They are given in Table 11. In [22], tests to obtain the final failure stress of the XP laminate are done by using $[90/0]_{2S}$ stacked specimens (according to ASTM D-3039). Comparisons of longitudinal tensile strength values between UD and XP for each situation are presented in Tables 12 and 13. XP laminate has lower strength than UD as in transverse tensile strength as seen in these Tables. One interesting result is that, matrix cracking does not happen until fibre failure in UD under longitudinal tensile loading without the effect of residual stress as seen in Table 13. This result emphasizes the importance of considering the residual stresses induced throughout the MRCC. It is seen that, a good validation is obtained between

experimental and predicted longitudinal strength values of UD and XP AS4/8552. Damage evolution in resin under longitudinal tensile loading in $z(3)$ direction with respect to Maximum Principal Stress criterion is presented in Figure 19. Damage initiates in resin at the fibre-resin interface in 90° ply. Final failure occurs when the fibre in 0° ply fails at $\varepsilon_3=1.87\%$. Damage path in the resin with respect to Bauwen's MVM criterion is sketched in Figure 20. Similarly, first matrix crack occurs in 90° ply and final failure occurs when the fibre in 0° ply fails at $\varepsilon_3=1.87\%$.

4 Conclusion

In this study, a micromechanical FE model is developed for calculating the elastic moduli, modelling the MRCC for detailed residual stress analysis and progressive damage assessment of XP AS4/8552. Results are compared with authors' previous study [12] and experimental data available in literature. It is seen that, the developed model is a good method for predicting mechanical behaviour of XP polymeric composites when experimental study is difficult to perform or relevant data are not sufficient. It is also seen that, consideration of process induced residual stress makes the approach more realistic which enables to predict each failure mode.

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6 References

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Fig. 1. Whole and quarter RVEs

Fig. 2. Temperature and linear thermochemical strain of 8552 resin throughout MRCC

Fig. 3. Development of elastic moduli and strain of 8552 resin throughout MRCC

Fig. 6. σ_{22} stress distribution due to transverse tensile loading

Fig. 4. Resulting deformations

Fig. 7. Different view of σ_{22} stress distribution due to transverse tensile loading

Fig. 5. σ_{11} stress distribution due to longitudinal tensile loading

Fig. 8. τ_{13} stress distribution due to longitudinal shear loading

Fig. 9. τ_{32} stress distribution due to transverse shear loading

Fig. 12. Residual Maximum Principal Stress distribution at the end of cure cycle

Fig. 10. Strain change in transverse direction during cure

Fig. 13. Raghava's MVM failure parameter distribution due to residual stresses at the end of cure cycle

Fig. 11. Residual Maximum Principal Stress distribution before cooling to room temperature

Fig. 14. Bauwen's MVM failure parameter distribution due to residual stresses at the end of cure cycle

Fig. 15. Transverse tensile stress-strain response of XP AS4/8552

Fig. 16. Damage evolution in resin under transverse tensile loading with the effect of residual stress

Fig. 17. Longitudinal stress-strain response under Maximum Principal Stress criterion for both resin and fibre

Fig. 18. Longitudinal-stress strain response under Bauwen's MVM failure parameter and Maximum Principal Stress criterion for resin and fibre respectively

Fig. 19. Damage evolution in resin under longitudinal (z) tensile loading with the effect of residual stress with respect to Maximum Principal Failure Criterion (resin)

Fig. 20. Damage evolution in resin under longitudinal (z) tensile loading with the effect of residual stress with respect to Bauwen's MVM criterion (resin)

$\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33}$				
PLANE	X	Y	Z	
x=0	R	F	F	
x=L	C	F	F	
y=0	F	R	F	
y=L	F	C	F	
z=0	F	F	R	
z=L	F	F	C	

Table 1. BCs for normal and thermal load modes

PLANE	τ_{12}			τ_{13}			τ_{23}		
	X	Y	Z	X	Y	Z	X	Y	Z
x=-L	F	C	R	F	R	C	R	F	F
x=L	F	C	R	F	R	C	R	F	F
y=-2L	C	F	R	F	R	F	R	F	C
y=2L	C	F	R	F	R	F	R	F	C
z=-L	F	F	R	C	R	F	R	C	F
z=L	F	F	R	C	R	F	R	C	F

Table 2. BCs for shear load modes

	This Study	[17]	
$E_1 = E_3$	21.00	20.88	GPa
E_2	10.50	10.48	GPa
G_{13}	3.44	3.42	GPa
$G_{21} = G_{23}$	3.07	3.07	GPa
$\nu_{13} = \nu_{31}$	0.14	0.14	
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{32}$	0.37	0.37	

Table 3. Predictions of "Composite #2" in [17]

	UD	XP		
	[12]	FEM	EXP.	
E_1	133000	71844	69223	[22] MPa
E_2	9755	12870	-	MPa
E_3	9755	71844	69223	[22] MPa
G_{12}	5228	3827	-	MPa
G_{13}	5228	5530	-	MPa
G_{32}	3194	3827	-	MPa
ν_{12}	0.267	0.443	-	-
ν_{13}	0.267	0.038	0.037	[22] -
ν_{21}	0.0196	0.079	-	-
ν_{23}	0.527	0.079	-	-
α_1	0.232	3.55	3.1	$10^{-6}/^\circ C$
α_2	40.03	56.4	53.7	$10^{-6}/^\circ C$
α_3	40.03	3.55	3.9	$10^{-6}/^\circ C$

Table 4. Glassy properties of UD and XP AS4/8552

Time	ϵ_1 (%)	ϵ_2 (%)	
t_{GP}	$-1.39141 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.6550	UD [12]
t_{VP}	$-8.507 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-0.3060	
t_{CP}	-0.00164	-0.3580	
t_{END}	-0.01776	-0.9330	
$t_{VP} - t_{GP}$	$-8.501 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-0.9700	
$t_{CP} - t_{VP}$	$-7.886 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-0.0430	
$t_{END} - t_{CP}$	-0.01612	-0.5750	
t_{GP}	$-2.8246 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.3035	XP
t_{VP}	-0.00763	-0.5823	
t_{CP}	-0.01117	-0.6456	
t_{END}	-0.07098	-1.4685	
$t_{VP} - t_{GP}$	-0.00761	-1.8860	
$t_{CP} - t_{VP}$	-0.00354	-0.0633	
$t_{END} - t_{CP}$	-0.05981	-0.8230	

Table 5. Comparison of shrinkage strain during MRCC

	UD [12]	XP
$\alpha_1 (10^{-6}/^\circ C)$	1.01	3.7
$\alpha_2 (10^{-6}/^\circ C)$	36	51.4
$\alpha_3 (10^{-6}/^\circ C)$	36	3.7

Table 6. CTE Predictions of AS4/8552

	UD	XP
$\alpha_1 (10^{-6}/^\circ C)$	0.21	3.1
$\alpha_2 (10^{-6}/^\circ C)$	33.3	53.7
$\alpha_3 (10^{-6}/^\circ C)$	34.7	3.9

Table 7. CTE Measurements of AS4/8552

Resin Criteria	UD [12]	XP
Max. Princ.	0.55	0.83
Raghava	0.61	1.06
Bauwen	0.64	0.82

Table 8. Failure parameter values due to residual stresses at the end of the MRCC of AS4/8552

Resin Criteria	UD [12]		XP
	σ_y^T	σ_z^T	σ_v^T
Max. Princ.	84	78	48 <i>MPa</i>
Bauwen	61	58	44 <i>MPa</i>

Table 9. Predicted transverse tensile strengths of AS4/8552 with residual stress

Resin Criteria	UD [12]		XP
	σ_y^T	σ_z^T	σ_v^T
Max. Princ.	102	85	86 <i>MPa</i>
Bauwen	103	86	90 <i>MPa</i>

Table 10. Predicted transverse tensile strengths of AS4/8552 without residual stress

Final Failure			
UD	[21]	2207	<i>MPa</i>
	[22]	2064	<i>MPa</i>
XP	[22]	1030	<i>MPa</i>

Table 11. Experimental values for longitudinal tensile strength of AS4/8552

	Resin Criterion	Matrix	Fibre	
UD	Max. Princ	1438	2388	<i>MPa</i>
	Bauwen	1070	2385	<i>MPa</i>
XP	Max. Princ	198	1172	<i>MPa</i>
	Bauwen	95	1174	<i>MPa</i>

Table 12. Predicted longitudinal tensile strengths for AS4/8552 with the effect of residual stress

	Resin Criterion	Matrix	Fibre	
UD	Max. Princ	-	2424	<i>MPa</i>
	Bauwen	-	2424	<i>MPa</i>
XP	Max. Princ	610	1137	<i>MPa</i>
	Bauwen	648	1153	<i>MPa</i>

Table 13. Predicted longitudinal tensile strength of AS4/8552 without the effect of residual stress